

Studies on the Adsorption and Desorption of Methylene Blue on and from Vermiculite and Asbestos

D. K. DE*, J. L. DAS KANUNGO and S. K. CHAKRAVARTI

Department of Chemistry, University of North Bengal Dist. Darjeeling, W. Bengal

Manuscript received 14 October 1972; revised 4 April 1973; accepted 7 July 1973

The adsorption data of methylene blue (MB) on H-vermiculite and H-asbestos are seen to fit in with the Langmuir equation within the concentration range studied. The exchangeability of the adsorbed MB by inorganic and organic ions from their respective clay-complexes follows the order: Na < K < NH₄ < H < Mg < Ca < Ba << CTA < CP for both vermiculite and asbestos. The values of the Langmuir constants as well as the selectivity coefficients of the desorbing cations point to the fact that MB has greater affinity for vermiculite than asbestos surface. From the adsorption data vis-a-vis the structural characteristics of the adsorbate and adsorbents it appears that the orientation of the dye on the mineral surfaces is predominantly flat.

THE adsorption of cationic dyes, although believed to be primarily an exchange reaction¹, is dependent upon various factors such as molecular size², molecular geometry of the sorbate², dye-dye interaction³ as well as the surface characteristics of the sorbent^{4,5}. In this paper are presented the sorption and desorption characteristics of the cationic dye, methylene blue on and from vermiculite, a two dimensional layer lattice silicate and asbestos, a naturally occurring secondary mineral having one dimensional or chain structure. The desorption of the clay-bound MB has been followed with inorganic and surface active quaternary organic cations such as cetyl pyridinium ion (CP⁺) and Cetyl trimethyl ammonium ion (CTA⁺).

Experimental

The vermiculite was obtained from the Geological Survey of India and judged to be pure vermiculite from X-ray diffraction studies. Clay fractions of minus 2.0 μ were isolated and converted into the H-form as described earlier⁶. The H-form of asbestos clay fraction was obtained by washing repeatedly with N/5 HCl instead of H-resin treatment. The cation exchange capacities (cec) determined by titration with Ba(OH)₂ in presence of normal BaCl₂ are 133.0 and 4.0 me/100 g for vermiculite and asbestos respectively. The experimental techniques employed for studying adsorption and desorption of MB on and from the clays are similar to those reported earlier⁶. The percentages of the clay-dye complexes used for studying desorption are 0.29 and 0.90 for vermiculite and asbestos respectively.

Results and Discussion

The adsorption isotherms of MB on H-vermiculite and H-asbestos and the corresponding reciprocal graphs are shown in Fig. 1. They are characteristic of the Langmuir type of isotherm. Both the value of

V_m (51 me/100 g), the amount of dye required to form a complete monolayer, calculated from the slope of the linear graph and the amount corresponding to the maximum adsorption (50.2 me/100 g) are much less than the cec of the vermiculite, namely 133 me/100 g. It is quite likely that the interlamellar space of vermiculite, which unlike montmorillonite, being limited to the thickness of about two water molecules⁷ (4.98 Å) is not fully accessible to MB. Moreover, it is also possible that the initially sorbed MB prevents, in a physical sense, entry of further dye ions into the interior of the interlamellar space.

Fig. 1. Adsorption isotherm and Langmuir plot of MB on vermiculite (a & b) and asbestos (d & c). (curves a and d refer to x, y and x', y' axes respectively).

For the sorption of MB on H-asbestos the value of V_m (3.0 me/100 g) compares well with the plateau of the isotherm which is about 3.08 me/100 g. However, both the quantities are slightly less than the cec of

* R.B.C. College, Naihati, W. Bengal.

the mineral (4.0 me/100 g). The exchange of small inorganic ions by asbestos takes place on the exchange sites of the surface as well as in the cavities that obtain in its fibrous structure, but the latter are probably not accessible to the much larger dye ions. Consequently, the cec measured from the adsorption of Ba^{++} from $BaCl_2$ in presence of $Ba(OH)_2$ is greater than that calculated from dye adsorption. From the shape of the adsorption isotherms and sorption data, it is clear that no multilayer formation takes place within the concentration range of the dye studied. From the intercepts of the Langmuir plots (Fig. 1), the values of the constants are 19.7×10^2 and $16.7 \times 10^2 M^{-1}$ for vermiculite and asbestos respectively. The higher value of the Langmuir constant indicates higher heat of adsorption of MB on to the vermiculite than asbestos and also binding of the dye to the higher energy sites of the adsorbent.

The average dimensions of the MB molecules¹ are 16 \AA^2 in length, 7 \AA^2 in width and 4 \AA^2 in thickness. The resonance structures of the dye locate four positive charge centres on MB and these structural considerations assign to MB a predominantly flat orientation (coverage 112 \AA^2) on the clay surface. However, other possibilities such as edge-on² (coverage 64 \AA^2) or end on coverage (28 \AA^2) are not entirely excluded. It is to be noted that the flat position is possibly attended with the minimum

171 \AA^2 and 110 \AA^2 for CV and MG respectively) are 745 and $723 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ respectively. Taking an average surface area of $734 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, the coverage area of MB on vermiculite from the adsorption data comes out to be 68 \AA^2 . Therefore, we are inclined to conclude that MB molecules can not be oriented in a flat mono molecular layer. The presence of MB aggregates at the surface of vermiculite may reasonably be assumed. However, the specific surface area of the asbestos calculated from the adsorption of crystal violet in a similar manner is $69 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$. From this value the coverage area per MB molecule as obtained from the sorption data is about 109 \AA^2 . The existence of a flat monolayer of adsorbed MB molecules on to the surface of asbestos may easily be surmised.

Figs. 2-3 and Table 1 show the results of desorption of the clay-bound dye with inorganic and large organic ions. It may be observed (Fig. 3) that the exchange of the asbestos bound MB proceeds almost linearly with concentration with the inorganic ions except by Ca^{++} at higher concentrations. The linearity of the graphs indicates the proportionality of the dye desorbed with that of the added electrolyte over the concentration range studied. It can be seen from the Figs. 2 and 3 and selectivity coefficient values (Table 1) that both in the case of vermiculite and asbestos the exchangeability of the inorganic

Fig. 2. Desorption of MB from MB-vermiculite by different ions. (curves 1-7 and 8-9 refer to x, y and x', y' axes respectively).

potential energy. The lower values of the dye adsorption capacities of the clays compared to their cecs also suggest that a part of the adsorbed molecules lie flat, thereby making some of the exchange sites inaccessible to those trying to accommodate themselves on the mineral surface in an end-on or edge-on position. The specific surface areas of the vermiculite determined from the adsorption of crystal violet (CV) and malachite green⁸ (MG) assuming flat orientation in each case (coverage area⁴

ions with the clay-bound dye is much less than the surface active ions *i.e.*, CTA^+ and CP^+ . The strong adsorbability of these cations⁹, their distinct detergent effect and geometrical relationship to the clay surfaces¹⁰ are responsible for their good exchangeability with the sorbed dyes. Again between the two surface active ions the desorbing efficiency is in the order $CP^+ > CTA^+$, which may be correlated with the lower critical micelle concentration of the former¹¹.

The distribution and selectivity coefficients have been calculated as in our previous paper⁶, assuming the ion exchange equilibrium as

where the bar refers to the clay phase and *Z* is the valency of the desorbing ions.

The values of the selectivity coefficients (Table 1) may be placed in the sequence : Na < K < NH₄ < H < Mg < Ca < Ba << CTA < CP for both vermiculite and asbestos. Table 1 also makes it apparent that the values of the selectivity coefficients are much less than 1.0 indicating a higher affinity of the dye for the clay surfaces in comparison with the desorbing ions. It can also be seen from Table 1 that the values of the selectivity coefficients of the desorbing ions are higher with asbestos than those

of vermiculite. Therefore, the relative binding strength of MB for the minerals is vermiculite greater than asbestos. The lesser affinity of MB for asbestos is also reflected in the lower value of the Langmuir constants compared to that of MB adsorption on to vermiculite as mentioned earlier. This is also expected from the structural architecture of the two minerals. The negative charge originating from the isomorphous replacements in the case of 2 : 1 lattice minerals like vermiculite may be said to be "smeared out" instead of being located on particular sites on the surfaces. On the other hand, in the case of asbestos possessing a chain or fibrous structure, one may think of some sites having a charge deficit where the positively charged centres of the dye molecules get adsorbed. Since the inter layerspace will not be available in the later case and the exchange sites are mainly the broken bonds on the exposed surface, the adsorption is likely to be weak whereas in vermiculite the cationic species of the dye ions will find a stronger field of attraction.

Fig. 3. Desorption of MB from MB-asbestos by different ions. (curves 1-6; 7-8 and 9 refer to x, y; x', y' and x'', y'' axes respectively).

TABLE 1—DESORPTION CHARACTERISTICS OF MB FROM MB-VERMICULITE(V) AND MB-ASBESTOS(A) BY DIFFERENT IONS

Electrolyte used	Concentration of electrolyte (M)	Distribution Coefficient		Selectivity Coefficient	
		V	A	V	A
1 : 1 electrolyte					
NaCl	1.5 × 10 ⁻²	0.06	0.019	0.22 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.13 × 10 ⁻⁵
KCl	"	0.064	0.028	0.29 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.25 × 10 ⁻⁵
NH ₄ Cl	"	0.10	0.030	0.77 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.34 × 10 ⁻⁵
HCl	"	0.12	0.109	1.1 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.46 × 10 ⁻⁵
2 : 1 electrolyte					
MgCl ₂	"	0.16	0.072	4.5 × 10 ⁻⁶	7.36 × 10 ⁻⁵
CaCl ₂	"	0.18	0.073	5.4 × 10 ⁻⁶	7.52 × 10 ⁻⁵
BaCl ₂	"	0.19	0.079	6.1 × 10 ⁻⁶	8.68 × 10 ⁻⁵
Quaternary ammonium salt					
CTABr	0.5 × 10 ⁻³	49.4	18.8	1.8 × 10 ⁻²	5.16 × 10 ⁻²
CPCl	"	99.4	23.6	7.6 × 10 ⁻²	8.52 × 10 ⁻²

References

1. C. S. BROOKS. *Kolloid Z. & Z. Polym.*, 1964, 199, 31,
2. W. S. RAMCHANDRAN, K. P. KACKER and N. P. PATWARDHAN, *Amer. Mineral*, 1962, 47, 165.
3. K. BERGMANN and C. T. O'KONSKI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, 67, 2169.
4. W. W. EWING and F. W. J. LIU, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1953, 8, 204.
5. U. HOYMANN, H. KOTTENHAHN and H. MORCOS, *Angew. Chem. Intern. Eng. Ed.*, 1966, 5, 242.
6. D. K. DE, S. K. CHAKRAVARTI and S. K. MUKHERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 44, 743.
7. J. W. GRUNER, *Amer. Mineral.*, 1934, 19, 557.
8. D. K. DE, J. L. DAS KANUNGO and S. K. CHAKRAVARTI, (Communicated).
9. D. J. GREENLAND and J. P. QUIRK, *Proc. Nat. Conf. Clays Minerals*, 1962, 9, 484.
10. S. K. CHAKRAVARTI, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1959, 7, 27.
11. D. K. DE, S. K. CHAKRAVARTI and S. K. MUKHERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 119.